

Source misrepresentation on the origin of COVID-19

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Abstract. A *Nature* news piece written by Dr. Amy Maxmen, published on 27 February, 2022 opened by falsifying a source, claiming that a preprint by Gao et al. had concluded the exact opposite of what it in fact concluded; the same falsehood continues to be repeated elsewhere. I submitted a correspondence to *Nature* on 24 November, 2022 concerning this, it being understood that, for correspondences, 15 days with no reply is a rejection. *Nature* did not reply, nor issue a correction. Here is the correspondence, for the public record.

A *Nature* news piece by Dr. Amy Maxmen, published on 27 February, 2022, concerning the origins of the COVID-19 pandemic, misrepresents a source [1].

The cited preprint by Gao et al., documenting authorities' search for environmental samples in and around the Huanan Seafood Market (HSM), concluded that the data “highly suggests the SARS-CoV-2 might have derived from *Homo sapiens* in the HSM,” and that “the market might have acted as an amplifier due to the high number of visitors every day”: i.e., that HSM was not the spillover site, but only an early super-spreader [2].

Yet the *Nature* news piece claimed that Gao et al. “trace[d] the outbreak back to a massive market that sold live animals, among other goods, in Wuhan, China”: the opposite of what Gao et al. in fact concluded.

Although the news piece is months old, the same false claim has continued to be repeated: for instance, David Quammen's recent *Breathless* falsely claims that Gao et al. “bolstered” and was in “evidentiary synergy” with two preprints arguing for a HSM spillover [3]. It thus still requires correction.

To preserve public trust in science, it is essential to ensure accurate scholarship, reporting, and editorial fact-checking. This is always the case, but it is especially the case for a topic as politicized as the origins of COVID-19. If authors wish to *argue* that Gao et al.'s finding of a single lineage-A sample at HSM proved their own conclusion wrong, they should do so, not distort that source's conclusion.

References

[1] Maxmen, A. (2022). Wuhan market was epicentre of pandemic's start, studies suggest. *Nature* **603**, 15–16. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-00584-8>

[2] Gao, G. et al. (2022). Surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 in the environment and animal samples of the Huanan Seafood Market [preprint]. Research Square. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1370392/v1>

[3] Quammen, D. (2022). *Breathless: The Scientific Race to Defeat a Deadly Virus*. Simon & Schuster.